

A Study on Expectations of Livestock Buyers and Sellers with Reference to Agriculture Produce Market Committees of Satara District

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It is important to study livestock seller's and buyer's expectations about market committees because it sheds light on their requirements, worries, and opinions about how the market is run. By being aware of these expectations, market committees can better accommodate seller's and buyer's requirements and improve the efficiency and fairness of the market by customizing their services and rules. A more open and sustainable cattle trading environment is also promoted when seller expectations are met, since this builds mutual confidence and collaboration between sellers and market committees. The research conducted with an objective to study the expectations of livestock buyers and Sellers who participate in trading at Agriculture Produce Market Committees of Satara District. The data is collected from 341 livestock buyers and 384 livestock sellers about the facilities provided by the market committees. The structured questionnaire is prepared to collect the data. The collected data is analyzed by z-test. The results show that market committees are capable to fulfill the expectations of the livestock buyers as well as sellers.

Keywords: apmc, livestock traders, livestock expectations

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1. Introduction

Livestock is very important aspect of Indian economy. About 20.5 million people depend upon livestock for their livelihood. The contribution of livestock is about 16% to the income of small farmers. It provides livelihood to two-third of rural community. In respect of Satara district, the livelihoods of many poor farmers depend on the sale of their agricultural outputs in the market. Since the livelihood of the Satara district is highly dependent on the livestock and the cash income from livestock, identifying all the potentials and constraints in the livestock trading and its performance efficiency analysis help to provide them with alternative markets that reducing cost and increase the benefit they deserve. Traditionally the agricultural produce was sold by the farmers in the village or nearby places. So farmers were unable to get fair price to their livestock. So the State's enacted their APMC acts to set up regulated agricultural markets so as to ensure that farmers get a fair price for their produce. They provide place, where farmers come and sell their livestock. It is important to see whether market committees fulfill the expectation of buyers and sellers or not.

2. Objectives of the Study

To study the expectations of livestock buyers and Sellers who participate in trading at Agriculture Produce Market Committees of Satara District.

3. Hypothesis

H₀: Expectations of buyers and Sellers are not fulfilled by APMC's.

H₁: Expectations of buyers and Sellers are fulfilled by APMC's.

4. Importance of the Study

It is important examine the expectations of livestock purchasers in order to comprehend livestock buyers behavior and develop techniques that work. Market committees can improve their services and promotional activities by understanding buyer's preferences, financial constraints, and required quality requirements. Understanding expectations helps market committees in the cutthroat livestock market increase consumer happiness and scale of market.

Market committees can increase overall market efficiency, reduce delays, and improve transaction processes by having a better understanding of the expectations of cattle merchants. Better operational flow is ensured by meeting traders' expectations for seamless, prompt, and transparent transactions. Fair pricing and transparency in price decision are frequently expected by livestock traders. Market committees can improve pricing systems, stop middlemen from taking advantage of them, and encourage price transparency by looking at their expectations. Properly maintained infrastructure, including weighing systems, storage facilities, clean premises, and auction yards, is expected by traders. Both buyers and sellers gain from the improvement of physical infrastructure that results from identifying discrepancies between expectations and reality.

5. Research Methodology

Data Required:

The data regarding Agriculture Produce Market Committee, infrastructural facilities, marketing conduct, livestock market structure, intermediary channels etc. is required.

Data Sources:

For the present study data will be collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Primary data is collected from the participants of livestock market (buyers and Sellers) with the help of a structured questionnaire for collecting livestock information.

Sampling:

In Satara District, there are 31 Agriculture Produce Market Committees (10 primary and 21 sub-agricultural). 14 Agriculture Produce Market Committees out of the 31 that exist perform cattle trade. Every week, livestock dealers exchange their animals at the market yard. For the study, all 14 Agriculture Produce Market Committees were chosen. The APMC samples are chosen using the census approach.

The average buyers in selected 14 APMC's from the year 2020-21 to 2023-24 are 2,545 out of which the data will be collected from 341 respondents. The total samples calculated are proportionately divided among selected 14 APMC's.

Total samples are calculated at 95% confidence level at 5% level of significance. The average sellers in selected 14 APMC's from the year 2020-21 to 2023-24 are 9,299 out of which the data will be collected from 384 respondents. The total samples calculated are proportionately divided among selected 14 APMC's.

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The collected primary and secondary data is analyzed and interpreted by the researcher. The primary data is collected to understand the role of market committees, fulfillment of expectations of buyers and sellers, understand the market practices and to identify the determinant for effective livestock trading.

6.1. Buyer's Response about Fulfillment of Expectations

Researcher has tested this hypothesis on the basis of responses given by buyers and sellers. Here researcher has used z test for proportion of categorical variables with 15 questions of Buyers and 16 questions of Sellers with responses "5 = Much better than expected", "4 = Better than expected", "3 = Equal to expected", "2 = Less than expected", "1 = Much less than expected".

Table 1: Expectations of Buyers from APMC's

Sr. No.	Questions	Mean	P Value	Decision	Expectations from APMC
1.	Behavior	4.20	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
2.	Security	4.74	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
3.	Communication	2.46	0.9568	Accept H0	Not Fulfilled
4.	Personalization	3.88	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
5.	Innovation	3.91	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
6.	Confidentiality	4.03	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
7.	Infrastructure	3.56	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
8.	Technology	4.90	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
9.	Supervision	2.38	0.0932	Accept H0	Not Fulfilled
10.	Grievance Assistance	3.07	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
11.	Price Information	1.78	0.0522	Accept H0	Not Fulfilled
12.	Broker's Transactions	3.85	0.0501	Accept H0	Not Fulfilled
13.	Commission	3.01	0.0109	Reject H0	Fulfilled
14.	APMC Charges	4.11	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
15.	Licensing	4.69	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled

(Source: Compiled by Researcher)

From the above table it is seen that according to buyers, expectations have been fulfilled about the behavior of staff, security, confidentiality, charges charged by market committees, licensing etc. At the same time they according to them, services, Supervision and brokers transactions are not as expected On the other hand expectations are fulfilled regarding communication with officials, Personalization of services received from the market committee, Innovation in the services, Technology used by the market committee, Police Personnel supervision or assistance, Accurate price information of livestock, Commissions charged by the brokers in the Market. This indicates that 60% of the buyers much better than expected from the facilities provided by the APMC.

6.2. Seller's Response about Fulfillment of Expectations

The sellers expect some things when they come at market committee to trade the livestock. The five point likert scale used to know whether the expectations have been fulfilled not. The scale was much better than expected, better than expected, equal to expected, less than expected, much less than expected. The respondent could choose any one from these five options to show the degree of fulfillment of expectation.

Table 2: Expectations of Sellers from APMC's

Sr. No.	Questions	Mean	P Value	Decision	Expectations from APMC
1.	Price	3.969	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
2.	Behavior	4.448	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
3.	Security	4.622	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
4.	Communication	3.013	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
5.	Personalization	2.667	0.0143	Reject H0	Fulfilled
6.	Innovation	2.815	0.0002	Reject H0	Fulfilled
7.	Confidentiality	3.815	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
8.	Infrastructure	3.154	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
9.	Technology	2.167	0.0321	Reject H0	Fulfilled
10.	Supervision	3.068	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
11.	Grievance Assistance	4.057	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
12.	Price Information	1.919	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
13.	Transactions (Brokers)	1.945	0.0501	Accept H0	Not Fulfilled
14.	Commission	1.966	0.0022	Reject H0	Fulfilled
15.	APMC Charges	3.971	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled
16.	Licensing	4.685	0.0001	Reject H0	Fulfilled

(Source: Compiled by Researcher)

From the above table, it is seen that seller's expectation are not fulfilled about the communication with officials, personalization of services received from the market committee, innovation in the services, technology used by the market committee, accurate price information of livestock, transactions through brokers and commissions charged by the brokers in the market. At the same time market committees fulfilled the expectations about the price of livestock behavior, infrastructure, confidentiality, grievance assistance, transaction charges charged by market committees, licensing etc. Negative response to the transaction through brokers is due to the fact that buyers experience that transaction through brokers due to concerns about added costs, lack of transparency in pricing, and potential for misrepresentation of animal quality. Direct transactions allow buyers to negotiate directly with sellers, ensuring better control over pricing and quality assessment without intermediary fees or uncertainties.

This indicates that 51% of the sellers much better than expected from the facilities provided by the APMC. From the above tables 4.105 and 4.106 of expectations from buyers and sellers with respect to Agriculture Produce Market Committee researcher obtained p value form the hypothesis testing and if the p value is less than the significance level (0.05 in our case) then it results in rejection of null hypothesis. In the decision column on the above tables (2.1 and 2.2) from buyer's 14 out of 16 and seller's 26 out of 26 question's responses said that there is strong evidence that researcher reject the null hypothesis (H₀) i.e. expectations of buyers and sellers are not fulfilled by that Agriculture Produce Market Committee that means alternative hypothesis (H₁) is accepted i.e. expectations of buyers and sellers are fulfilled by that Agriculture Produce Market Committee in the livestock trading.

(Note: In our result researcher proves that there is strong evidence that expectations of buyers and sellers are fulfilled by that Agriculture Produce Market Committee but researcher also kept in mind that two factors from buyers like provide communication service with buyers and police personnel supervision make efficient changes for fulfill the expectation of buyers from Agriculture Produce Market Committee.)

7. Conclusion

In respect of hypothesis 51% of the sellers are happy about the facilities provided by the APMC, which resulted in acceptance of alternative hypotheses i.e. expectations of buyers and sellers are fulfilled by that Agriculture Produce Market Committee in the livestock trading. Livestock buyers anticipate fair trading practices in livestock markets, seeking transparency, honesty, and equitable treatment. Fairness ensures confidence in pricing, animal quality, and transaction processes, fostering trust between buyers and sellers. It's essential for sustaining long-term relationships and the overall integrity of the livestock trading ecosystem.

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